

The Cybertory virtual molecular laboratory: How does it serve the teaching community? Report from users

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Cybertory at the Biomodel.UAH website is a platform that allows students to perform simulated experiments involving genetic analysis on DNA samples [1-4]. This originated from a former platform developed by Robert M. Horton that offered two assays using RFLP: detection of beta-globin variant producing haemoglobin S and sickle cell disease, and forensic test of a crime scene sample against several suspects. After I converted it from a format specific for the defunct Netscape web browser into one compatible with modern browsers (HTML5), we used it over some years with our students to complement our wet lab practicals with a virtual one diagnosing the HbS genotype. Later on, the laboratory was expanded to do PCR experiments and has since kept widening to allow many kinds of topics using either or both techniques (see table). Since this expansion in 2017 I set an access control to gather some information on which groups were using it worldwide (Spanish and English versions). Despite the control by password, the tool remains open and free to use by anyone interested.

RFLP assays	PCR assays	PCR + RFLP
β^S -globin diagnosis	Paternity test (CoDIS STRs)	RET protooncogene
Forensic analysis	Forensic analysis (CoDIS STRs)	
Vegetable oil adulteration (cpDNA)	Dairy product adulteration (mtDNA)	
	Cytochrome P450 polymorphism	
	Celiac disease polymorphism	
	Plant resistance gene	
	Viral infection test (SARS-CoV2 vs. Influenza)	

Recently, with occasional users having requested access once while others using it repeatedly for up to 7 or 8 years, I decided to run a survey about why, how and what were instructors using with their students, and which were their perceptions regarding contribution to the learning process. Presenting the output of this survey is the aim of the current article.

A questionnaire with 11 items, prepared with *Wooclap*, was presented by email through an online link to all teaching staff that had requested access since 2017 up to February 2025. Number of addressees was ca. 600, in 45 countries. Responses received were 170, from 21 countries (figure 1). That supports the results to be considered significantly relevant, with worldwide use across diverse educational systems.

Following is the content of the questionnaire.

Report from users of Cybertory, 2025

- Q1 Which country are you in?
- Q2 Educational level of your students. (If you use it in several, please fill a survey for each)
- Secondary education / High school
 - Professional training degree / Technical degree
 - University (college, BSc)
 - Master / Posgraduate degree
- Q3 Number of students in each group using the Cybertory. (You can check more than one)
- up to 10
 - between 11 and 30
 - between 31 and 50
 - between 51 and 100
 - over 100
- Q4 Total number of students using the Cybertory in an academic year. (You can check more than one)
- up to 10
 - between 11 and 30
 - between 31 and 50
 - between 51 and 100
 - over 100
- Q5 Which experiments in Cybertory do your students work on? (You can check more than one)
- Beta S globin (sickle cell anemia)
 - DNA sequencing
 - Forensic analysis by RFLP (with restriction enzymes)
 - Forensic analysis using PCR
 - Paternity test
 - Cytochrome P450 genetic polymorphism
 - Celiac disease: genetic diagnosis
 - Dairy products adulteration
 - Vegetable oil adulteration
 - Resistance gene in plants
 - Viral infection: COVID or common flu
 - RET protooncogene (MEN2A)
- Q6 In which stage do you use the Cybertory, within your teaching strategy? (You can check more than one)
- Previous to the real laboratory (wet lab), as preparation or training.
 - After the real laboratory, as reinforcement, review or to expand the experiments.
 - Instead of the real laboratory, which is not feasible.
- Q7 Motivation for using the virtual laboratory
- We don't have the equipment and techniques available in real laboratory.
 - Even though we have the equipment, the economical cost is not affordable.
 - As a complement to what we have available in the real laboratory.
- Q8 Your perception of how much your students value these aspects (1= little or no value; 3= neutral; 5= much valued)
- Accessibility to the virtual laboratory.
 - Ease of use of the simulation.
 - Contribution to understanding of techniques and to learning.
 - Degree of realism (not just visual, but functional) as compared to a real experiment.
 - Attractive character of the theme of the experiment.
- Q9 Your own evaluation, as instructor, of these aspects: (1= little or no value; 3= neutral; 5= much valued)
- Accessibility to the virtual laboratory.
 - Ease of use of the simulation.
 - Contribution to the understanding of techniques and to learning.
 - Degree of realism (not just visual, but functional) as compared to a real experiment.
 - The economical considerations (against similar commercial products more sophisticated)
- Q10 Please value your overall satisfaction with the tool, as an instructor. (Scale 1 to 10)
- Q11 Please value how you perceive your students' overall satisfaction with the tool. (Scale 1 to 10)

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of instructors who have provided information on the use of Cybertory with their students. (Q1)

Figure 2. Educational levels in which Cybertory is being used. (Q2)

Q3,4

Number of students using the Cybertory

Figure 3. Size of the groups of students and total number of students with whom activities are carried out in this virtual laboratory. (Q3, Q4)

Q5

Which experiments in Cybertory do your students work on?

Figure 4. Types of experiment that have achieved greater application with the groups of students. (Q5)

Q6

In which stage do you use the Cybertory, within your teaching strategy?

Figure 5. Stage within the teaching strategy when the virtual laboratory is used. (Q6)

Q7

Motivation for using the virtual laboratory

Figure 6. Motivations that have brought teachers to the use of Cybertory with their students. (Q7)

Q8,9

Features perceived as valuable

Figure 7. Virtual laboratory features valued as positive by students and teachers. (Q8, Q9)

Q10,11

Overall satisfaction with the tool

Figure 8. Global satisfaction with the Cybertory tool. (Q10, Q11)

The results are self-explanatory. Some key points may be highlighted: the report from users matches several features that were anticipated, while designing the simulated environment, as desirable for achieving an effective and profitable learning using this kind of platforms. Among them:

- Overcome limitations that, in many circumstances, can hinder teaching laboratories: space, time, instrumentation, samples, reagents, safety requirements.
- Enrich the learning experience, providing a complement to real experimentation, opportunities for review or reinforcement, familiarization with techniques outside the physical laboratory, or access to modern techniques not available in the centre.
- Remarkably, it is interesting to avoid closed resources where everything flows as expected and the result is fixed and predictable. It is much more suitable to allow the possibility of performing true experiments when there are diverse samples, modifiable parameters, that lead to different results according to the design that has been chosen to carry out the experiment.
- The use of different samples for each user and on each occasion, randomly assigned, provides different results, even negative results (unsuccessful experiments), as in real life.
- Allowing free exploration encourages inquiry and hence training on experimental design and the scientific method: setting hypotheses, adjustment of experimental conditions, observation of results, extraction of conclusions.

References

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